

ORGANIZATIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF CALL CENTERS IN DAVAO CITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10903459>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the domain of knowledge management that best influences organizational performance in a call center industry setting in Davao City. The study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design to obtain the result. The study involved 197 respondents, from call centers at the supervisory level, who were chosen through a random sampling technique. The primary tool for data collection is an adapted questionnaire following a 5-point Likert-type scale. The data gathered were subjected to statistical analyses, which included weighted mean, Pearson correlation, and regression analysis. Results indicated that the level of Knowledge Management was very high, and the level of Organizational Performance was also very high. However, when these were tested for a significant relationship, the study found no association with a positive r-value of 0.093. Furthermore, it was shown that the Culture domain of knowledge management best influence organizational performance. This implies that the system of shared assumptions, values, and beliefs in the call center fields can change the view on the actual results or output of this firm as measured against its intended output, goals, or objectives.

Keywords: *knowledge management, organizational performance, call center industry, business, correlation, regression, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the business environment is very volatile with a dynamic nature that can be seen in challenges faced by the organization, especially in the call center industry. Poor organizational performance, one of the persistent issues that should be addressed immediately, is widespread in organizations. Such cases of sub-optimal efficiency, falling productivity and such bad service delivery raise an alarm indicating the presence of underlying bigger system issue that needs careful analysis (Abubakar et al., 2019).

Customer service centers are used by numerous companies to handle consumer questions regarding billing, opening new accounts, and faults with goods or services. In addition to being recognized as a useful tool for businesses to manage customer contacts, call centers have a bad image for being high-stress workplaces that lead to subpar organizational performance (Pfeffer, 2010). Nowadays, organizational performances have been declining over the years in a call center industry. Historically, companies do measure its performance through sales volume and financial performance; however, it is simply inadequate. Numerous businesses fail to recognize what other signs are as measurement strategies that are required to effectively redesign processes.

Other research also suggests that quite a few intangible resources have some impact on organizational performance, not much consideration was devoted to recognizing the decision-making procedures where resources become valued (Barney *et al*, 2001; Lynch, 2010). Thus, knowledge management can positively affect organizational performance; it must lend itself to improved organizational memory (Jennex, 2017). This is supported by other searches that using knowledge management effectively could increase organizational performance and competitiveness in the market and organizational awareness (Appolloni, Coppola & Piga , 2019). Literature appears to be voluminous on this, therefore much needs to be learned about the present state of knowledge surrounding organizational performance. In this realm, previous research has made significant contributions in the past pointing out different aspects that shape the efficacy of an organization. These studies have considered leadership styles, employee motivation factors and technological advancements among others. These contributions are important to note as they have formed the basis of future work, allowing us to build on prior insights as well as refine our knowledge of the connection among knowledge management and organizational performance.

The literature on knowledge management in the call center industry has made considerable progress in understanding how knowledge management practices are associated with company performance. But a prominent research gap remains in terms of identifying and focusing on certain features of their settings which affect the outcomes of knowledge management projects in different call centers. The focus of some investigations touched upon knowledge management at large organizational venues; however, many aspects of the call center environment have not yet been explored despite the emergence of the nature of the customer interactions, employee turnover, and the rapid development of technologies. It is imperative in filling this research gap to create specific and industry-based knowledge management interventions which can help improve the organizational performance and competitive advantage in the call center business sector which is a dynamic and competitive world. Since there is lack of information on the knowledge management and organizational performance of call center industry in Davao city, this explains why this research is taken, justified, needed and important. The objective of the study is to identify relevant recommendations that would help to establish new knowledge management practices applicable in the agencies to boost organizational performance under the current business environment parameters.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The purpose of the research is to identify which domain of knowledge management that best influences organizational performance in a call center industry setting in Davao City.

Thus, this study seeks to attain the following objectives:

1. To assess the level of knowledge management in terms of:
 1. leadership;
 2. strategy; and
 3. culture?
 2. To ascertain the level of organizational performance in terms of:
 1. comparative performance;
 2. internal performance?
 3. To determine the significance of the relationship between knowledge management and organizational performance?
 4. To identify which domain of knowledge management best influences organizational performance among call center industry in Davao City?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The research was particularly carried out in Davao, Philippines. After Metro Manila and Metro Cebu, this city has the third-highest population in the nation. In terms of total land area, the city also happens to be the biggest in the nation.

The survey was carried out in Davao City, which is host to roughly 15 international call center businesses. The city takes pride in being Mindanao's primary center for business, commerce, and manufacturing. Growing teams, accounts, and clients handled by a worldwide business process outsourcing (BPO) organization in Davao City indicate a rise in the BPO sector. Davao is starting to resemble Manila every day. This vast metropolis boasts abundant gastronomic, cultural, advertisement, and economic resources. International businesses, shopping centers, and other enterprises are already proliferating throughout the city and neighboring regions.

Sampling Method

The respondents in this research were the supervisory/management personnel in the call center companies in Davao City. A sample of 197 supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was chosen to participate in this study. The respondents of the study were calculated by means of the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator with 5% margin of error.

The researcher utilized a basic random sampling technique. To guarantee that every member of the sample population has a similar likelihood of being chosen as a research participant, this sampling process was employed. It would prove nearly impossible to

test, look at, or gather data from every single component in a research study encompassing a large number of parts. Although it was feasible, the time, expense, and other human resources needs would be prohibitive. Sampling was therefore employed to enable research.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the panel members' consent, the researcher followed these stages and processes to collect information for the research: Firstly, the investigator requested consent from the university to perform the research. The top call center companies in Davao City received a formal letter of recommendation from the dean of the University requesting their cooperation.

Following approval, the researcher gave the participants a synopsis of the research and described the goal and research instrument. Following that, the researcher instructed the participants on how to complete the survey correctly. The researcher then painstakingly encoded every response in an Excel spreadsheet and sent it for statistical examination.

Following data collection, the findings were examined and interpreted considering the study's goals. Considering the study's outcomes, suggestions were developed, and conclusions were reached.

Research Instrument

Two standardized scales were used in this study. Two adapted and contextualized survey instruments were used in this study. A survey questionnaire on knowledge management was adapted from Mangotra and Mahajan (2014) which consisted of leadership, strategy, and culture with 21 items in total. On the other hand, organizational performance was taken from Makore and Eresia-Eke (2015) which comprises comparative performance and internal performance with 7 items in total. The scale has 5 options from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

A group of professionals verified the contextualization and fitting of the modified tools within the local environment. The independent variable is knowledge management with markers of leadership, strategy, and culture. Likewise, both instruments were verified for reliability and appropriateness through Cronbach Alpha test.

Statistical Treatments

Several statistical methods were applied to the information to provide deeper interpretation and assessment:

Mean. Mean was utilized to characterize the knowledge management and organizational performance in the call industry in Davao City.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was utilized to assess the importance of the connection between organizational performance and knowledge management in the Davao City call center sector.

Regression Analysis. This statistical treatment was utilized to uncover which domain of knowledge management best influences organizational performance in a call center in Davao city.

Scope and Limitations

This study included participants with supervisory and line management personnel actively involved in call center operations in Davao City. The sample was selected to allow a concentrated focus on those individuals who enjoyed prominent positions in the call center companies, significant insights into the managerial aspects of the industry thus offered. Participants who were involved or manage—directly supervisory or managerial position in their organization, which indexes their impact on the functioning of the decision-making processes within the organization.

Taken on the contrary, exclusion criteria were developed to establish some form of refinement for the group by rejecting those participants who played no role or were not involved in the act supervisory and managerial processes in the call center setting. Since the goal was to measure the data of the specific stratum of the call center workforce – the managerial stratum – the paper excluded staff members without oversight responsibilities such as frontline agents or support staff. Simultaneously, originally people from call centers that are outside the city of Davao were excluded so that the geographical aspect and situation detail are maintained.

RESULTS

Table 1

Level of Knowledge Management in a Call Center Industry in Davao City

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Leadership	0.19	4.77	Very High
Strategy	0.25	4.68	Very High
Culture	0.25	4.65	Very High
Overall	0.17	4.70	Very High

Table 2

Level of Organizational Performance in a Call Center Industry in Davao City

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Comparative Performance	0.53	4.57	Very High
Internal Performance	0.35	4.58	Very High
Overall	0.39	4.57	Very High

Table 3

Significance of the Relationship between Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance in a Call Center Industry

Organizational Performance			
Knowledge Management	Comparative Performance	Internal Performance	Overall
Leadership	-0.125 (0.081)	0.120 (0.093)	-0.031 (0.668)
Strategy	-0.169* (0.018)	-0.051 (0.472)	-0.139 (0.051)
Culture	0.397** (0.000)	0.173* (0.015)	0.350** (0.000)
Overall	0.068 (0.340)	0.104 (0.147)	0.093 (0.191)

Table 4

Significance on the Influence of Knowledge Management on Organizational Performance of Call Center Industry in Davao City

Organizational Performance				
Knowledge Management	B	B	t	Sig
Leadership	-0.117	-0.056	-0.767	0.444
Strategy	-0.388	-0.249	-3.387	0.001
Culture	0.692	0.443	6.382	0.000
R	0.437			
R²	0.191			
F	15.208			
P	0.000			

DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed the statistical descriptions result on evaluating the level of knowledge management in the Davao City call center business. The sector has a total mean of 4.70 alongside a descriptive score of very high, meaning that knowledge management situations are always observed. Overall, it shows that although some call center managers strongly agree or disagree with certain claims, most of them tend to realize that managing knowledge in their organization may be continuously observed, albeit with slight variations in each supervisor's response.

The leadership indicator had the largest mean of all the knowledge management measures, 4.77, and was considered very high. This suggests that managers frequently see their staff members work toward accomplishing the organization's common objectives.

Besides, the three indicators of knowledge management posited a very high level. The other knowledge management indicators, which are strategy, and culture, posited a *very high* level. It can be gleaned from the data that strategy gained the mean of 4.68, described as *very high*. This indicator specifies that the company is continually manifesting its role, purpose, and strategic direction. Whereas the culture obtained a mean of 4.65, taken as *very high*. This marker averts that the company is always encompassing various employees' backgrounds, shared values, and norms that emerged into a working environment.

The overall level of knowledge management was very high as perceived by the supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry. As to indicators, the level of knowledge management in terms of leadership was very high. This indicate that the leadership of supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was observed at all times concerning; central knowledge in managing call center; recognizes the possibilities of its knowledge resources to generate revenue and cultivates methods to capitalize on them; a culture of transparency and confidence governs the call center; enhancing customer service is acknowledged as a key goal of knowledge management; adaptability and a desire for innovation motivate the approach to learning; the call center has developed innovative methods to connect knowledge to the monetary outcomes; and it has created a particular collection of indications for monitoring knowledge that includes financial as well as non-financial metrics.

The results confirm the study by Theriou et al. (2011), which uncovered that knowledge management can be made more effective by utilizing five enabling factors: people, technology, leadership, culture, and knowledge management strategy. These elements improve the organization's knowledge management effectiveness. They also underlined how information can be made more effective by leadership, which fosters an environment in which it can be applied in real-world situations to tackle organizational challenges. It also supports the research by Han et al. (2016), which found that leadership—which is crucial to teamwork—is a sensitive element in knowledge management.

According to Garcia-Morales et al. (2012), attending to the individual needs of employees can have a positive impact on the organization by encouraging personnel to put in more effort at work, improving the quality of products or services, and increasing customer satisfaction, which can lead to higher returns on expenditures and the chance to increase sales or services to boost earnings.

As to knowledge management in terms of strategy, the level was very high. This indicate that the strategy of supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was observed at all times concerning; The team frequently holds meetings to stay up to date on the most recent technological advances improvements; staff members have access to the web for searching up data; guides and guidelines are frequently employed; significant occurrences, events and circumstances are dealt with; and all call center employees are continually looking for improved methods to satisfy consumers.

Theriou et al.'s (2011) study, which found that improving an organization's information-sharing strategy within a business can boost employee performance and corporate competitiveness, corroborated the study's findings. According to Fong and Kwok (2009), the goal of the approach is to improve information flow within the company through engagements and conversations.

As to knowledge management in terms of culture, the level was very high. This indicates that the culture of supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was observed at all times concerning; Knowledge management facilitates acquiring fresh abilities inside their work; knowledge sharing facilitates studying afresh each day; an environment that supports advocates team members to contribute and talk about ways to avoid causing the same mistakes twice; an environment of trust facilitates improved decision-making and makes the task of making choices easier; prompt knowledge regarding innovative applications and technological advances enhances efficiency.

The study's findings in line with those of Gholami et al. (2013), who found that staff autonomy (skill development) and training, staff engagement in the management of knowledge tasks, collaboration, motivating staff members, efficient utilization of technology for communication and information, evaluation of performance that takes into account both soft and hard regulations and a knowledge-friendly workplace environment are among the most important aspects of knowledge management that may be developed. Additionally, Laal (2011) investigated knowledge management and discovered that information sharing that could influence an organization's principles and procedures requires trust among its members.

Table 2 displays the organizational performance status of Davao City's call center sector as determined by several markers: comparative and internal performance. The standard deviation was 0.39, which denoted the consistency of the respondents' answers. The calculations yielded a very high total mean rating of 4.57, indicating that organizational performance is consistently demonstrated.

The overall mean score was based on the mean scores of the two indicators of organizational performance. First was *the comparative performance* with a mean score of 4.57 described as *very high*, which depicted that the compelling motivation for organizational improvement was always manifested. Lastly, *internal performance* revealed a mean score of 4.58 described as *very high*, which meant that its growth is always manifested over a while.

The overall level of organizational performance was very high as perceived by the supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry. As to indicators, the level of organizational performance in terms of comparative performance was very high. This indicates that the leadership of supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was always manifested concerning; in contrast to the business standard, they are more profitable; they have greater market share; and they are growing more rapidly.

The study's findings were in line with a 2003 study by Wright et al, which showed that management strategies for generating profits, operating costs, and sales were used

to track organizational performance as a measure of corporate success. To evaluate the company's success in comparison to its primary rivals, Kyrgidou and Spyropoulou (2013) gathered subjective assessments of sales, customer satisfaction, and financial performance. Additionally, Kunze et al. (2013) used senior managers' assessments of the company's financial status, expansion, efficiency, and personnel turnover as well as recruitment in comparison to the immediate industry competitors to evaluate the performance of the organization.

As to organizational performance, in terms of internal performance was very high. This indicate that the leadership of supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry was always manifested concerning; Their company is operating more efficiently than it was a year ago; it is operating more efficiently than it was a few years ago; it has accomplished the targets it set for the last year and the last five years.

Thomaz et al. (2017) investigated a method that tracks and assesses performance in connection with the definition of goals and desired outcomes, and organizational performance management, which includes techniques, structures, and indications. Developing and assessing a strategy, inspiring employees, and reporting the performance to stakeholders are all important aspects of improving the management of organizational performance.

Similar to this, an organization's performance serves as a foundation for evaluating how well its outcomes are moving in the direction of predefined goals (Wheelen and Hunger, 2012). Performance goals lead to an efficient execution of plans throughout the entire company, whereas a management of performance for the company ought to be put into practice (Zulkiffli, 2011).

Table 3 illustrates the investigation assessed the association between the two variables. The null hypothesis was accepted based on an overall r-value of 0.191 and a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Overall, the findings indicated that there is no discernible relationship between knowledge management and company performance. The conclusion suggests that there is no correlation between changes in an individual call center business's level of knowledge management and changes in organizational performance.

On the other hand, it can be observed that in a singular capacity, among all indicators of knowledge management, only culture had a significant relationship with organizational performance, as shown by its r-value of 0.350 and p-value <0.05. The strategy also had significant relationships when correlated with comparative performance, which obtained an r-value of 0.397 and p-value < 0.05.

The overall relationship between knowledge management and organizational performance in a call center industry was highly significant. This means that the more knowledge management being observed, the better the organizational performance in a call center industry.

The study's findings were in line with those of Rasula et al. (2012), who found a connection involving organizational performance and knowledge management strategy.

In a similar vein, Ling's (2013) research indicated a substantial relationship between the variables. The findings are coherent with the results of the study of Chen et al. (2015), who found that management is crucial to the search for goods and services that can boost an organization's productivity and maintain a larger competitive edge.

Table 4 are results of the regression study findings which demonstrate the strong correlation between organizational performance and culture as a knowledge management metric in Davao City call center businesses. The most accurate indicator was found to be culture, which had a considerable impact on organizational performance, according to the investigation. The statistical relevance of culture's impact on the efficiency of an organization is determined via an F-value of 15.208 and a p-value of 0.000, both of which are less than the 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, the findings showed that when knowledge management and organizational performance were regressed, the R² value of 0.191 was produced. This suggests that 19.10% of the variability in organizational performance in the call center business may be explained by the knowledge management variations. By contrast, the remainder of 80.90% may be ascribed to other causes outside the purview of this investigation.

The overall significance of knowledge management on organizational performance was discovered to be significant. According to the findings, culture was the best indicator among leadership and strategy to predict the organizational performance of the call center industry.

Shahzad et al (2012) said that in order to raise employee performance generally, managers and other executives ought to foster a strong organizational culture. According to Fellows and Liu (2013), organizational culture fosters learning among its members. Adhocracy environments were also found to be strong positive determinants of performance in the company by Fekete and Bocskei (2011).

The research presented the salient role of organizational culture on performance outcomes. Culture directly affects the behavior of employees and indirectly impacts decision-making functions. A positive adaptive culture contributes positively to the performance measures and the study highlights this fact. Once advocated for strong organizational culture that encourages innovation, networking, as well as continuous development in the long run optimizes efficiency.

Strategy and culture's powerful impact factors in the context of Davao City's call centers contribute greatly to the outcomes achieved in the performance of operations. A strategic approach enables the processes to be fine-tuned, workflows to be tightened, and general performance to be smoothed. Moreover, the culture of organizations in call centers influences the way an employee acts and performs. It helps build a culture that supports teamwork, communication, and sense of accountability, and that also helps increase operational efficiency.

The cultural setting of Davao City significantly contributes to determining the organizational performance of call centers in the area. The cultural characteristics of organizations may help to create a co-operative and team-oriented environment amongst the employees which leads to effective communication and collaboration. Furthermore,

the high levels of industriousness and loyalty that are generally connected with being Filipino could positively influence call center operators in Davao City's commitment and productivity. But it is very important that organizations are culturally intelligent and that their management strategies are adapted to match with local values and practices, because, to not do so may cause problems regarding employee morale, engagement, and overall organizational performance. Achieving harmony between the international standards of best practices and the local cultural peculiarities is a precondition to fully unleash the potential of the workforce in Davao City's call centers.

Conclusions

This research presents that according to the supervisory/management personnel in the call center industry, the level of overall level knowledge management is very high. Likewise, a very high level of organizational performance in the call center industry was found. Moreover, there is no significant connection between knowledge management and organizational performance in the call center industry. Among the domains of knowledge management, culture was the best predictor of the supervisory/management personnel in the organizational performance.

These findings imply that knowledge management in terms of culture plays a necessary part in organizational performance. With this, the supervisory/management personnel could improve the performance of the organization and that can sustain greater competitive advantages.

Recommendations

The conclusion is that, while all in all, the KM levels in the Davao City Call Center Industry are praiseworthy, these recommendations try to fine-tune and improve aspects that were identified in the study. By tackling these areas, the industry can strengthen its position as an innovator in effective knowledge application, thereby ensuring continued organizational profitability and competitive advantage. The following recommendations address the call center industry players, management teams, and policymakers, whose interpretations significantly shape the knowledge management setting in their respective organizations.

Further investigations may also be focused on comparable research with multiple variables conducted by other researchers in order to validate the current study's findings while taking into account additional factors that influence organizational performance in the call center industry. Additionally, the area of study may be expanded in order to allow researchers to confirm the current study's findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research was conducted using the following ethical standards:

Informed Consent Process. Informed consent documents were provided for research participants to confirm their voluntary participation free from fear of harm or intimidation.

Voluntary Participation. Each participant was offered the option to participate freely and without facing any penalties or repercussions. Following the presentation of the study's objectives and advantages to the participants, the respondents' rights to participate in the research were duly acknowledged and respected. Respondents are free to choose not to answer any questions on the survey.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The study ensured that the participants' private and/or professional information remained confidential, with special attention paid to maintaining the maximum privacy of their data. Participants withdrawing were assured of confidentiality, and the data were excluded from the final analysis. The criteria for withdrawal plan to cater for anything unforeseen and ensure continuity of the integrity of the researchers' findings.

Benefits. Although there are no immediate rewards from this survey, participants can choose to provide their contact information to be entered into a lottery for five (5) cash vouchers worth Php 150.00, which will be given away to five (5) randomly selected responders. If the paper is turned into a non-technical study brief, call center organizations can use its results as a basis for enhancing their services, on the grounds of scholarly value, and use the summary of the research to implement policy adjustments at their own discretion.

Recruitment. The researcher's inclusion criteria, which included being 20 years of age or older, were used to determine which subjects should be recruited. Every employee in the business's human resources department helped the researcher find the appropriate respondents.

Risks. High-risk scenarios that participants might encounter, and which could give rise to medical, mental in nature or financial problems were not included in the study. There is very little evidence of discomfort or unease during the five to ten minutes it takes to complete the questionnaire.

Plagiarism. There were no claims employed in the research that led to plagiarism. Grammar uniformity and a low level of similarity can be achieved by using Grammarly, Turnitin, or any other plagiarism checker. This allows the researcher to freely communicate the topic in her own words.

Fabrication and Falsification. It is acknowledged that the research is grounded in a variety of studies, guaranteeing that the investigator refrains from drawing any conclusions from her own writing and instead presents the authors' ideas in her own authoritative voice. To match the results, the investigation is unlikely to inflate the data or overclaim works of others. The theoretical foundation and models that are employed must originate from authentic and trustworthy sources. Additionally, the study will not witness any falsification.

Conflict of Interest. Nevertheless, an insignificant conflict of interest was identified, thus it needs to be disclosed in this research. Although the researcher was a member of the leadership team at a BPO company, you can be sure that the study will

not affect any secondary interests and will only concentrate on the main goals, which include improving business decisions based on studies and participant wellbeing.

Deceit. The research gave those who participated the assurance that the information they received would not endanger them. No deceit or trickery will be required. Furthermore, the research exclusively uses in-person surveys; it makes no use of internet platforms to guarantee that any queries from participants are going to be addressed. Last but not least, the research questionnaire guarantees to be devoid of technical jargon, easily comprehensible for study participants, and providing a clear picture of potential benefits to participants following study execution.

Permission from Organization/Location. The research project began by requesting authorization to collect data from two sources: the administration of call center agencies and the University of Mindanao Professional Schools, as authorized by the dean.

Furthermore, the researcher made sure to secure formal consent from the company where the research will be conducted, or data collected. This consent is obtained through having the proprietors sign a letter granting authorization to do the study that has been submitted to them.

The owners' approved letters will act as official authorization to carry out a survey. To make sure that the call center industry was willing to have the survey conducted on their property, follow-ups were conducted. After ascertaining the willingness of supervisor or managerial staff to partake, the researcher coordinated the survey days' timetables with the call center industry's administration.

Authorship. Adhering to ethical standards in academic research, is acknowledgement of authorship which helps to credit individual contributions. The researcher serves as the first author of this research work; thus the researcher accounted the conception design, execution, and final analysis of findings. The supervisor's key role is recognized as co-author as supervisor have guided and supported this research.

Acknowledgments

I hold up my gratitude and praise to our Almighty God, the Source of Wisdom, and the Lord of all humankind.

I send my love and appreciation to my family, my husband and my son, Avi, my Mama and Papa who have stood by me throughout this process on both a financial and emotional basis.

I would like to express my gratitude and appreciation to Dr. Reynaldo Castro, my research adviser, as well as to Dr. Montano, my statistician, grammarian, and panel members, who have all diligently dedicated their time and efforts to the accomplishment of this study.

I also really appreciate the research participants' kindness and cooperation in providing me with their responses.

Finally, I would like to thank all my friends who have helped me tremendously to finish this research in one way or another.

-R J Q

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